

EFFECTS OF DISORDERED TOUGHENING PARTICLES ON UNIDIRECTIONAL FIBER REINFORCEMENT PERMEABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Compared to traditional metal materials, composites are generally brittle and have a low resistance to crack initiation and propagation. Researchers have addressed this issue by incorporating particulate based fillers to increase material properties like fracture toughness. However, additives can be detrimental to processing variables like permeability and the consistency of parts. This limits more widespread applications because liquid composite molding processes can become prohibitively difficult. During the manufacture of particle and fiber composites, the infiltrating fluid can experience particle filtration, pressure buildups. Hence, a robust body of research investigating particle effects on resin infiltration is needed. Generally, it is difficult to distinguish the effects of particles from other processing variables; for instance measured permeability can vary by an order of magnitude. Here, an effort is made to numerically predict the effects of incorporating particles and toughening agents on the steady state, single phase permeability, of randomly aligned composite reinforcement fibers. Specifically, variations in filler particle size and concentration were studied. Over 500 simulations were conducted on three dimensional geometries, with particle volume fractions between 0-10.5%, and fiber volume fractions of 60-64%. The particles were randomly inserted into the domain, fixed in space, and solved for as part of the mesh. These particles have mass and occupy physical volume in the computational domain. Baseline permeability results of fiber geometries without particles compared well with analytical and numerical results. The findings of this study include permeability as a function of particle volume fraction, independence over a small range of particle sizes, and independence from various drag laws numerically implemented. The results also indicate that this is an area of interest for future work.

1 INTRODUCTION

Processing of composites is complicated and varies significantly from processing traditional metal based materials. Liquid composite molding (LCM) is a class of composite manufacturing techniques that is commonly used to manufacture finished composite parts. This class of methods includes resin transfer molding (RTM) and vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM). Variations to these methods have been created for trade secret and specific commercial applications. Particulates can be composed of a number of toughening and strengthening particles and have been used to advance

composite mechanical properties [1]–[4], but these inclusions can add a layer of difficulty to the manufacturing process.

The critical processing parameter in LCM simulations is permeability, which drives the mold filling time and pressure distribution. Permeability is a function of the fiber reinforcement geometry, fiber volume fraction, and fiber type. If the fiber preform and boundary conditions are not well designed, then the mold will be filled slowly or incompletely. Additionally, effects like fiber washout can occur where the fiber arrays are deformed and the designed mechanical properties will not be achieved in the manufactured composite. Fiber reinforcement can have a filtration effect when particles are flowing along with a fluid [5]. The particles can cause complete flow blockages if the particulate sizes are inappropriate or tend to agglomerate reducing the interconnected nature of the porous material.

The flow resistance with fiber reinforcement increases rapidly with increasing fiber volume fraction, while the particulate incorporation can have a large effect on infusions creating added resistance to flow. If the production of parts by liquid composite molding processes are desired, it is important to understand the effects that particles will have on the infusion parameters. In mold design, it can be difficult to identify what the final flow properties will be like before a tool is built because there are so many coupled parameters. Poor mold design will lead to poorly finished parts with large quantities of air entrapment.

Composite manufacturers started to incorporate particulate additives in production for special purposes such as electrical conductivity [1], thermal conduction [2], flame retardance [3], and cost reduction [4]. To achieve these ends, it is important to distinguish between micro- and nano-particles. Nano-particles (1E-9m) generally require a lower filler percentage than micro-particles (1E-6m) to achieve a designed effect like mechanical property improvement [6]. Some particles incorporated into a composite may bridge the gap between the standard particle sizes, encompassing features of both scales. For example, exfoliated graphene is generally 3-5nm thick but can easily have an effective diameter of 5-15 μ m.

Two main methods exist for incorporating particles into laminated composites. One uses liquid composite molding where the particles are dispersed into a resin system and then the resin is infused into the fiber reinforcement. In some cases, the high surface area of particles and the large aspect ratio of some particles leads to significant increases in resin viscosity [7]. Additionally, this approach can cause filtration of the particles by the fiber reinforcement and result in gradient dispersion of the particles. A second approach coats the particles directly onto the fiber surfaces in a sizing approach [8]. This approach can reduce the issue of gradient material properties but permeability reductions still exist. However, in one case the investigation of transient permeability of a plain weave S-glass fabric with graphene nano-platelets found that permeability increased due to an interply spacing effect [9].

Particle filled resins and particle coated or filled preforms are different. Particle filled resins with particles in suspension can have viscosity increases as well as thixotropic properties. The issue of filtration leads to gradient mechanical properties and is also a design parameter that must be understood. All this combines to change the resin flow and can lead to dry spots, poor saturation, and changed cure times [4]. Well dispersed particles in the preform may have smaller effects on filtration but may still have important effects on permeability. The effect on permeability would also be a function of particle size.

This investigation is a first attempt at discovering the effects of spherical particles on a flow field in composite manufacturing and their effect on permeability. Numerical tools are utilized to predict the effects of incorporating particles and toughening agents on the steady state, single phase, permeability of unidirectional, randomly aligned, composite reinforcement fibers. Specifically, variations in filler particle size and concentration at a single fiber volume fraction are simulated. The study was designed to simulate and model fixed particles with a future work to include transient particles and agglomeration. Over 500 simulations were conducted on three dimensional geometries, with particle volume fractions between 0-10.5% and fixed fiber volume fractions of 60-64%. The particles were randomly inserted into the domain, fixed in space, and solved for as part of the mesh. These particles have mass as well as occupying physical volume in the computational domain. Permeability of just the fiber geometries were taken as a baseline for permeability. Those results were

then compared with results from including particles and showed reasonable decreases in permeability. The findings of this study include permeability driven by particle volume fraction and independence from various drag laws numerically implemented. Results show an independence from particle size over a small range of particle diameters and no effects due to the randomness of the well distributed particle dispersion. The results also indicate that this is an area of interest for continued work.

2 FIBER REINFORCEMENT MODELLING

The fiber reinforcement modeling approach has been described in another paper [10]. For this study, the micro-scale is isolated for direct numerical simulations. One characteristic fiber geometry and packing at volume fractions of 60-64% are studied. This fiber volume fraction range was selected based on what is commonly seen in unidirectional tows. The fiber packing arrangement is forced to be identical at each volume fraction in order to remove the effects of packing arrangements on the results. Packing arrangement has been shown to affect the resulting permeability because of the blockage of preferential flow channels.

3 FLOW MODELING

Here, models for the longitudinal and transverse flow through fiber beds with incorporated particles are created. The solution for the permeability of flow perpendicular and parallel to the fibers has been conducted in 3D with the finite volume code FLUENT. The computations are done at low flow rates so that the creeping flow assumption is valid. This implies that inertial forces are neglected and the results for permeability should result in linear pressure gradients. The single phase, saturated flow, is simulated to simplify the case. The solid phases are solved for but only one fluid phase is considered. Two phase fluid flow disturbances like capillary effects and saturation are often present in manufacturing mold fills but will not be considered here.

The simulations were performed for fiber volume fractions of 60-64% in increments of 1% volume fraction. In each simulation there were 10 fibers in the computational domain using a geometry generation code from previous research [10]. A characteristic geometry for 10 fibers can be seen in Figure 1. In the volume cell, the fiber surfaces are assumed to have a standard no slip, wall boundary condition. The boundaries of the volume are assumed to be translationally periodic and are matched to opposing faces. The inlet condition is a pressure inlet and an atmospheric pressure outlet is assumed. The steady state laminar flow conditions are assumed to accurately represent the flow that takes place under experimental permeability measurements. The model results output are the maximum and minimum pressures as well as the volume weighted average velocity. A tetrahedral mesh is generated for the unit cell. Currently, this approach allows for a consistent mesh between particle volume and packing. However, a new mesh is required for each fiber volume fraction and the particles must occupy a minimum number of mesh elements in the domain. This requires that the mesh be fine enough to incorporate the particle size of interest. As the particles become smaller, an increasingly fine mesh is required, and corresponding computation times increase.

Figure 1: The fiber geometry for the majority of simulations with a set of parallel flow boundary conditions. The fluid region is gray and the fibers are green. The fiber volume fraction here is 60%.

The properties of the fluid used in the numerical simulation were motor oil, often used in experimental investigations of permeability (Motor Oil, Viscosity $0.24\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$, Density 709 kg/m^3) [11]. It is envisioned that, the micro-scale permeability with particulate incorporation could be used to aid in the prediction of the macroscopic, component level permeability. This would be done using the results of these simulations as averaged permeability inputs for tow geometries on meso-scale permeability simulations. The component level permeability is of manufacturing interest because it models the impregnating resin in liquid composite molding without having to account for every individual fiber and tow leading to a more computationally efficient solution.

4 MACROSCOPIC PARTICLE MODEL

Typical particle tracking methods assume that particles are point masses that do not interact [12]. When trying to consider relatively large particles in a flow field, large meaning larger than multiple discretized cells, special considerations have to be made. Factors such as a blockage of fluid volume, which directly affect permeability because of its effect on porosity, have to be taken into account. Further, the proper evolution of the drag force, particle-particle collisions, particle-wall collisions, torque, and friction dynamics can be significant for large moving particles [13]. In the macroscopic phase model, particles are treated in the Lagrangian frame of reference and each particle spans several computational grid points.

In modeling fibrous preforms for composite manufacturing, a porous media assumption is often valid. If the domain of interest is the micro-scale, the interactions between a well dispersed micro-particle phase and the computational domain has to be considered. Two critical problems that evolve during composite manufacturing with toughening particles include gradients in material properties caused by a filtering effect from the fiber preform and uneven particle dispersion caused by the flow and interparticle forces. Here, it is assumed that we have a well dispersed particle inclusion in our domain as in Figure 2. In order to simplify this first investigation and reduce computation time, particles are fixed in the domain to investigate their effect on the pressure distribution.

Figure 2: An isometric (A) and parallel flow (B) view are shown as a characteristic example of random particle incorporation at $1\mu\text{m}$ particle size and 1% particle volume fraction. An isometric (C) and parallel flow (D) view are shown as a characteristic example of random particle incorporation at $3\mu\text{m}$ particle size and 5% volume fraction. These particles are assumed to be fixed in space and not allowed to flow with the resin or affect the resin viscosity. The flow is treated as a single phase fluid and particles are allowed to partially exit the computational domain.

The Discrete Phase Model (DPM) works for some domains, but this treats a particle as a point mass and these point masses have the properties of the fluid as the particles move [12]. In this investigation of particulate incorporation, 1, 3, and $5\mu\text{m}$ particles are inserted with $9\mu\text{m}$ fibers. In the general use of the DPM model, the particles of interest are considered to be much smaller than the computational grid cell in the discretization. The modeling of particles that have mass and volume requires a different and unique approach. If properties such as permeability are of interest, this approach must also account for effects such as a change in geometry and a blockage of fluid volume.

The Macroscopic Phase Model (MPM) developed by Agrawal et al. [13] meets many of the needs stated for composite interactions with a dispersed particle phase. The model accounts for effects such as drag forces, particle torque, friction dynamics, particle-particle and particle-wall interactions. The model is designed for finite volume computational fluid dynamics solvers where direct numerical simulations (DNS) are avoided because of a large number of particles of interest. Furthermore, this model assumes that the particles of interest fill multiple computational mesh cells.

This model in the transient case, has the ability to track any particle through a volume, the most common way to do this is to use a Lagrangian frame of reference. Each particle is assumed to span several computational cells. Cells that contain at least one node within the region occupied by the particle are affected by the particle. Six degrees of freedom are assigned to each particle to account for the translational and rotational motions. However, in this first investigation the particles are forced to be fixed because of the time consuming transient simulations required for moving and interacting particles. At every computational time-step, the particle motion is described by a solid body velocity

and patched to the computational domain. This adds the momentum of the particle to the momentum of the fluid. In the future the effects of moving particles should be investigated more fully.

Body forces are included in the model natively. Drag forces and torque in a particle are expressed as the integral of linear and angular momentum respectively. When these forces are solved for they are then applied to iterate the new velocities and particle locations at the next time step. The drag and torque calculations for the particle can be seen in Agrawal et al. [13], [14].

$$Drag = \left(\sum_{\text{touched cells}} m_f (\bar{V}_f - \bar{V}_p) \alpha_p \right) \frac{1}{\Delta t} \quad (1)$$

$$Torque = \left(\sum_{\text{touched cells}} m_f (\bar{V}_f - \bar{V}_p) \cdot \bar{r} \alpha_p \right) \frac{1}{\Delta t} \quad (2)$$

Here, m_f denotes the mass of the fluid, V_f is the fluid velocity, V_p is the particle velocity, r is the radius vector from the fluid center to the particle center, α_p is the particle volume fraction in the domain. A particle volume fraction of one is assigned to fluid cells that are completely within the particle volume.

Partially filled computational cells are treated differently. The volume fraction for the particle in those cells is calculated by accounting for the effective cell nodes inside of the particle volume. The model has the ability to account for a continuous particle injection inlet as well and maintain an overall mass balance. When particles are continuously injected, a mass source term based on the displaced fluid per unit time is included in the model.

Particle collisions between walls and other particles are also accounted for in a model by purely kinematic and geometric considerations. The surface of walls and particles are identified and if a second particle comes in contact with the first wall or particle in a previous time step, a collision is registered. When this collision takes place, the particle velocity is projected onto the normal and tangential components of the reflected particle velocity. Within a time step, the minimum separation distance becomes less than or equal to the sum of their radii and is detected. The coefficient of restitution and friction factor are applied when appropriate. When particles come in contact with other particles, then the principle of conservation of momentum is applied to obtain the final velocity of both particles.

The model accounts for field forces and body forces like electrostatic or magnetic forces by a potential force model [13]. Inter-particle forces are described with:

$$F_i = \sum_j \frac{G_P M_i^{n_1} M_j^{n_2}}{R_{i-j}^{n_3}} \quad (3)$$

Where, F_i is the force on particle i , M_i is the particle mass, $R_{i,j}$ is the interparticle-distance. Model constants are defined for each particle describing the system as G_p , n_1 , n_2 and n_3 . Many of these constants come from empirical or analytical models for the reaction of a single particle. The sign of the model constants decides whether the field force is attractive or repulsive.

Written in the SCHEME programming language, a set of user defined functions (UDF) are used to implement the MPM model. Initial properties for a particle or set of particles are implemented by prescribing the initial position, velocity, density, and radius. Particles can be inserted into a domain as a point, line, or surface injection. Those particles can also be a continuous particle injection in both cylindrical and rectilinear coordinates. Further, particles can be injected into a domain randomly. To date, results on steady-state particles are all that will be presented and transient results will be presented in the future.

5 RESULTS

The results given below are computationally intensive and a large set of data was generated in order to obtain the figures. Figure 1 shows the characteristic geometry at 60% fiber volume fraction. This was meshed in order to run the fluids simulation and the mesh had to be correspondingly refined to reduce the nominal mesh size to have at least five fluid volumes inside of each particle. The

periodic boundary conditions are used to help make up for the reduced domain. Pressure inlets and outlets were applied here and the volume average velocity was calculated.

Figure 2 shows isometric (A,C) and parallel flow (B,D) views as a characteristic example of random particle incorporation. Figure 2 A and B show 1 μm particle size and 1% particle volume fraction inside of 60% fiber volume fraction geometry. Here, the small particles each incorporate multiple mesh volume elements and the particle velocity is fixed at zero. Figure 2 C and D shows a characteristic example of random particle incorporation at 3 μm particle size and 5% volume fraction. The particles only partially fill the computational domain due to their size in reference to the inter-fiber flow channels. Particles are assumed to be well dispersed, fixed in space, and not allowed to flow with the resin. Comparisons were made between allowing partial particles and only complete spheres in a computational domain. Little difference was seen between partial and complete particles in the domain.

Figure 3: The Effects of Drag Law Selection on Fixed Particles for Perpendicular Permeability. The particle volume fraction adds to the fiber volume fraction (60%) to become the global volume fraction.

Figure 3 shows drag law effects on perpendicular permeability for 5 μm particles. It can be seen that fixed particles in the domain are not largely different in their effect on the pressure drop through the domains from various drag laws. This was expected given that the particles have no momentum, for that reason the momentum deficit drag law has little effect. All permeabilities calculated for the same particle volume fraction, at the same boundary conditions, are nearly identical. Figure 4 reinforces the same results as in Figure 3 for a set of parallel flow cases. These results are the same trend seen with particles ranging in size from 0.5, 1, 3, and 5 μm .

Figure 4: The effects of Drag Law Selection on Fixed Particles for Parallel Permeability. The particle volume fraction adds to the fiber volume fraction (60%) to become the global volume fraction.

Figure 5 shows the non-dimensional perpendicular permeability vs. global volume fraction with particles sizes varied from 500 nm to 5 µm. The global volume fraction is the combination of the fiber volume fraction and particle volume fraction. The results are non-dimensionalized by the square of the fiber radius. The particle size was selected in order to investigate a small range of size variations, while the corresponding mesh was refined to meet the requirements for investigating the smallest particle and maintaining the minimum number of elements in that particle. Additionally, decreasing the particle size requires a further refined mesh and an increasing computation time. Figure 6 shows the fiber volume fraction fixed at 60% and the particles added in increasing global volume fractions up to 70%. The volume fractions studied were increased to see if any non-linearities could be identified. Results show an independence from particle size over a small range of particle diameters and no effects due to the randomness of the particle dispersion.

Figure 5: Perpendicular Permeability vs Global Volume Fraction. This case starts at 60% Fiber Volume Fraction and Increases in Volume Fraction by Increasing the Number of Particles Incorporated. The results of 150 perpendicular permeability simulations are plotted against volume fraction and colored by particle size.

Figure 6: Parallel Permeability vs Global Volume Fraction. This case starts at 60% Fiber Volume Fraction and Increases in Volume Fraction by Increasing the Number of Particles Incorporated. The results of 150 parallel permeability simulations are plotted against volume fraction and colored by particle size.

Figure 7: Perpendicular Permeability vs Global Volume Fraction. This case starts at 61, 62, 63, and 64% Fiber Volume Fraction and Increases in Volume Fraction by Increasing the Number of Particles Incorporated. Particle size is a constant 3 μ m here.

Figure 7 gives the perpendicular permeability versus fiber volume fraction by particle volume fraction. The results here are also non-dimensionalized by the square of the fiber radius. The initial fiber volume fraction is varied from 61-64% and then increasing particle volume fractions are added. These results are interesting because it seems that the fiber volume fraction has a larger effect on

decreasing permeability than well dispersed particles. This may be partially because the permeability will not monotonically approach zero at higher volume fractions as long as the pore network is interconnected.

6 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The effect of particle drag on fixed particles has been shown to have little effect on the results of permeability simulations because particles are fixed in steady-state simulations. Steady-state simulations are much faster to conduct and therefore a large number of steady-state results can be computed where the same number of transient results would require exponentially more resources. These steady state results could be useful for inputs into meso-scale permeability models for tow inputs already containing particles.

It is assumed that fiber volume fraction increases cause a more drastic decrease in permeability than increasing the volume fraction of particles because increased fiber volume fraction reduces flow channels, while well dispersed particles allow for more flow around them at the same volume fraction. Furthermore, the current simulations look at the effect of particles on the flow but is neglecting their ability to flow and change resin viscosity. This assumption has not been validated for a wide variety of cases and the applicability of this approach will only apply to a very select case of processing conditions. There will be a particle size threshold where the particles are too small to be treated as a part of the mesh and this approach will break down when the corresponding mesh is not sufficiently fine. This threshold is a function of the mesh element size and the particle size and maintains a minimum relative ratio of about 5 computational volumes contained in each particle.

The results are limited to predicting permeability on scales comparable to mesh element size because of the semi-direct numerical approach and the computational resources required. Important processing variables can be obtained in this manner including the velocity and pressure distribution. The permeability of unidirectional fibers, woven fabrics, and fiber preforms has been well studied, but permeability becomes more complicated when considering the effects of particulate incorporation into the fiber preform or resin system. For this reason, modeling research on the subject has been limited. During the manufacture of particle and fiber composites, the infiltrating fluid can experience high pressures, and permeability can be difficult to find. This is one attempt to distinguish the particle effects from the many other processing variables. This is one explanation for how preform permeability could vary due to local particle concentrations or by a lack of saturation.

Inclusions are another processing parameter that could be modeled in the approach given here. These inclusions could be made up of micro-scale voids, entrapped air bubbles, or other defects. As a tow or yarn is initially beginning to saturate, the advancing resin flow front tends to only partially saturate the volume as a function of time and pressure [15]. At any instant in time, this modeling approach could be used to approximate the volume fraction of resin saturation with the particles being treated as air bubbles. This would approximate the effect of partial saturation on permeability and could be used as a function of increasing permeability with increasing saturation as the fluid zone modeled trends towards complete saturation. Hence, incorporating partial saturation on the steady state, single phase, permeability of unidirectional, randomly aligned, composite reinforcement fibers could be achieved.

The variations in filler particle size and concentration at a fiber volume fraction trended down as was expected but did not directly follow the trend of the fiber volume fraction increases. The cause of this is assumed to be because the interconnected flow network is larger with spherical particles at a certain fiber volume fraction than the network is with cylindrical fibers at the same fiber volume fraction.

The results increase our understanding of particulate effects on manufacturing properties that are critical during liquid composite molding. Over 500 simulations were conducted on three dimensional geometries. Particle volume fractions were varied between 0-10.5% in order to investigate how increasing particle concentrations affect permeability. This was applied to 60, 61, 62, 63, and 64% fiber volume fractions in a 10-fiber, micro-scale domain.

Randomness of particles insertions seemed to have little effect because they were well dispersed in the domain. The fact that the simulations incorporated the particle mass as well as physical volume is

unique in computational approaches. The findings of this study include permeability effects from particle volume fraction. Results show an independence from particle size over a small range of particle diameters.

7 FUTURE WORK

The results of these simulations show a consistent drop in permeability with the incorporation of increasing numbers and volume fraction of particles. This is an appropriate first step in attempting to predict the permeability. The future work with this approach will investigate the effects of transient particles that are allowed to interact with each other as well as fiber reinforcement. Further, the corresponding drag laws investigated are expected to play a more important role once particles are moving. The transient clogging of flow channels by particle agglomeration will have an effect on permeability and quantifying that effect is a goal of future work. A more fully characterized set of materials with the effects of toughening particles on composite permeability would be useful. These models could be used as precursors to micromechanical models where the final properties and manufacturing effects of particulate incorporation could be more fully investigated. For instance, when particles are mechanically designed to be well dispersed but the liquid molding process does not accomplish this. Additionally, an in-house direct numerical simulation approach is being developed to repeat these results.

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